

Effects of interfacial defects of the p-CuO/n-TiO₂ on the CuO/CdS/TiO₂ solar cell performance

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Abstract

Due to its high absorption of solar energy and low heat emission, copper oxide has been used in a growing number of recent investigations. The crystal structure of CuO is monoclinic at 99.54°. There are four oxygen atoms firmly bonded to each copper atom. The results show a decrease in V_{oc} , J_{sc} , and η with increasing interfacial defect density, where V_{oc} decreases from 0.652 V at a defect density of 10^{10}cm^{-2} to 0.648 V at a defect density of 10^{14}cm^{-2} , J_{sc} decreases from 18.31 mA/cm² at a defect density of 10^{10}cm^{-2} to 13.20 mA/cm² at the efficiency defect density of 10^{14}cm^{-2} , F.F increases from 37.69% at the defect density of 10^{10}cm^{-2} to 46.87% at the defect density of 10^{14}cm^{-2} , η decreases from 4.51% at the defect density of 10^{10}cm^{-2} to 4.01% at the defect density of 10^{14}cm^{-2} . As the cross-section of carrier capture increases, the length of propagation will decrease, and thus the durability of the carriers will decrease. The results, are a decrease in V_{oc} with an increase in the cross-section ranges from 0.791 V to 0.776 V, J_{sc} from 27.69 (mA/cm²) to 20.60 (mA/cm²), F.F from 84.59% to 70.21%, and η from 18.53% to 11.24%.

Keywords: Interfacial defects; CuO; TiO₂; Solar cell; SCAPS-1D; Energy level; Carrier trapping

1. Introduction

A multitude of photoactive absorber materials have been used recently to produce a wide range of photovoltaic (PV) systems. Since silicon solar cells account for more than 90% of the worldwide solar market, they are the most extensively utilized type of solar cells.[1], even though they now operate at more than 26% efficiency[2]. Si-based solar cells are rather expensive, hence many efforts have been made to produce low-cost, high-efficiency solar cells. [3-6]It is expected that a safe and benign material such as TiO₂ would eventually be able to replace silicon-based solar cells. However, the use of TiO₂ as the active material in solar cells is still relatively new, and there are fewer papers on the subject.[7, 8]TiO₂ and CuO based heterojunctions are promising options for solar cell components and photocatalytic applications.. [9-11]. Materials used in P-type solar cells, such as absorber layers Cu₂O or CuO, have low direct band gaps between 2.0 and 2.6 eV.[12]and 1.0–2.1 eV [13], respectively. With a gap energy of over 3 eV, TiO₂ is an n-type semiconductor with a wide bandgap that is well-known for its many functions and potential as a material for dye-sensitized solar cells. [14, 15]. TiO₂ is regarded as a window layer or buffer material.[12].

2. Cell Structure

The solar cell structure is composed of (TiO₂ / CdS / CuO) as shown in Fig (1) Titanium dioxide (TiO₂) is the window layer, which is one of the transparent metal oxides and has a relatively large energy gap of about (3.2 eV). Then, the buffer layer Cadmium Sulfide CdS has a suitable energy gap of (2.4 eV) and works on tuning between the window layer and the absorption layer. Then comes the p-type (CuO) absorption layer, which has an energy gap that ranges from 1.21 to 1.51 eV (1.9eV).

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Figure 1 The solar cell structure

Table 1 Materials parameters used in the simulation

Parameters	Symbol (unit)	TiO2	CdS [16]	CuO
Thickness	W(μm)	0.3	0.1	Variable
Bandgap	Eg (ev)	3.2	2.4	1.5
Electron affinity	χ (ev)	4.2	4.2	4.070
Dielectric permittivity	εr	10	9	18.100
CB effective density of states	N _C (cm ⁻³)	2 × 10 ¹⁷	2.2 × 10 ¹⁸	2.2 × 10 ¹⁹
VB effective density of states	N _V (cm ⁻³)	6 × 10 ¹⁹	1.8 × 10 ¹⁹	5.5 × 10 ²⁰
Electron thermal velocity	V _n (cm/s)	1.0 × 10 ⁷	1.0 × 10 ⁷	1.0 × 10 ⁷
Hole thermal velocity	V _p (cm/s)	1.0 × 10 ⁷	1.0 × 10 ⁷	1.0 × 10 ⁷
Electron mobility	μ _n (cm ² /v. s)	100	100	100
Hole mobility	μ _p (cm ² /v. s)	25	25	0.1
Shallow uniform donor density	ND (1/cm3)	1 × 10 ¹⁷	1 × 10 ²¹	0
Shallow uniform acceptor density	NA (1/cm3)	0	0	Variable

3. Numerical simulation in SCAPS-1D

A one-dimensional solar cell modeling tool called SCAPS-1D was developed at the Department of Electronics and Information Systems (EIS), University of Gent, Belgium, and was used to numerically study the solar cell. Up to seven layers can be added to the software's cell definition panel to increase its suitability for simulating solar cells. Physical properties include bandgap, electron affinity, and dielectric permittivity, among others. [17]. The software's main role is the solution of semiconductor equations. We begin by writing a Poisson equation.. [18].

$$-\frac{d^2\psi}{dx^2} = \frac{dE}{dx} = \frac{q}{\epsilon_s} [p + n + N_D^+ - N_A^-] \dots \dots \dots [1]$$

where the concentration of donors is represented by N_D and that of acceptors by N_A; P is the hole density, n is the electron density, ψ is the electrostatic potential, E is the electric field, and ε_s is the relative permittivity.

The continuity equation can be obtained by using the relationship that follows.

$$\frac{\partial n}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{q} \frac{\partial J_n}{\partial x} + G_n - R_n \dots \dots \dots [2]$$

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} = -\frac{1}{q} \frac{\partial J_p}{\partial x} + G_p - R_p \dots \dots \dots [3]$$

where (G_p) is the rate of electron (hole) generation, (R) is the rate of electron (hole) recombination, and J_n (J_p) is the current density of electron (hole) (hole). Solving the Poisson and continuity equations yields the equations for the charge carrier diffusion and drift density.[19].

$$J_n = q(n\mu_n E + Dn \frac{dn}{dx}) \dots \dots \dots [4]$$

$$J_p = q(n\mu_p E + D_p \frac{dp}{dx}) \dots\dots\dots [5]$$

Where q The charge , μ_n (μ_p) are the mobility of electron (hole) , (E)electric field, (D) diffusion coefficient .The total current of the solar cell was calculated using the following formulas. [20].

$$I = I_0 \left(\exp \frac{qV}{nKT} - 1 \right) - I_L \dots\dots\dots [6]$$

where T is the temperature in Kelvin, K is the Boltzmann constant, and I_L is the current of light. To calculate the open circuit voltage (V_{oc}), which is the voltage that occurs when there is no current and is defined by the following equation.

$$V_{oc} = \frac{KT}{q} \ln \left(\frac{I_L}{I_0} - 1 \right) \approx \frac{KT}{q} \ln \left(\frac{I_L}{I_0} \right) \dots\dots\dots [7]$$

Where I_0 is the saturation current, which may be found using the equation below.

$$I_0 = A \left[\frac{q D_n n_i^2}{L_n N_A} + \frac{q D_p n_i^2}{L_p N_D} \right] \dots\dots\dots [8]$$

The length of electron and hole diffusion is represented by the diode's cross-sectional area, which is indicated by L_n and L_p . The relationship between the open circuit voltage and short circuit current is shown in the following relationship.

$$I_{sc} = I_0 \left(\exp \frac{qV_{oc}}{KT} - 1 \right) \dots\dots\dots [9]$$

where the following equations show the relationships between the variables V_{oc} , I_{sc} , η , and FF.[18].

$$FF = \frac{V_{max} I_{max}}{V_{oc} I_{sc}} \dots\dots\dots [10]$$

$$\eta = \frac{P_{max}}{P_{in}} \times 100\% \dots\dots\dots [11]$$

$$\eta = \frac{FF \times I_{sc} \times V_{oc}}{P_{in}} \times 100\% \dots\dots\dots [12]$$

The minority carrier lifts time, or the average amount of time needed to recombine minority carriers, must be determined. There is a link between it and the concentrations of doping and recombination. [21]:

$$\tau = \frac{1}{\sigma V_{th} N_t} \dots\dots\dots [13]$$

$$\tau = \frac{\Delta n}{R} \dots\dots\dots [14]$$

where N_t is the concentration of defects, V_{th} is the thermal speed, R is the recombination rate, σ is the capture cross section, and Δn is the concentration of surplus minority carriers.

The mobility of the charge carrier in bulk semiconductor material can have a major effect on a solar cell's performance..[22]. As The minority carrier diffusion length (diffusion length L_m) is largely dependent on mobility. Diffusion length is the average length scale over which a material can diffuse in a semiconductor before recombining. The definition of minority carrier diffusion length is given in Equation 15. [23].

$$L_{diff} = \sqrt{D \tau} \dots\dots\dots [15]$$

where τ is the minority carrier's lifespan and D is the diffusion coefficient. Equation 16 provides the relationship for D.

$$D = \mu \frac{KT}{q} \dots\dots\dots [16]$$

The carrier's mobility, charge, Boltzmann's constant, and temperature are denoted by the variables μ , q , and T , respectively.

The value of equation 16 will be substituted for equation 15 in that sequence, yielding equation 17.

$$L_{diff} = \sqrt{\mu \frac{KT}{q} \tau} \dots\dots\dots [17]$$

Equation 18 indicates that the mobility of minority carriers will have a major effect on the diffusion length. A solar cell's photocurrent will be improved by increased mobility because it will be more likely for photogenerated charge carriers to aggregate at the terminals. On the other hand, if mobility decreases, solar cell efficiency will also fall.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Effect of the energy level of interfacial defects of the p-CuO/n-TiO2 cell

In this part, we will study the effect of interfacial defects on the operation of the solar cell with the change in the defect level of the interfacial state in the donor-like state of the equivalence band, at the Gaussian distribution, while the other parameters remain constant without change. In the case of the donor alum, the results can be explained as in Figure (2).

Figure 2 The effect of the level of donor defects and the concentration of interfacial defects on the operation of the solar cell

The results show a decrease in V_{oc} , J_{sc} , and η with increasing interfacial defect density, where V_{oc} decreases from 0.652 V at a defect density of 10^{10}cm^{-2} to 0.648 V at a defect density of 10^{14}cm^{-2} , J_{sc} decreases from 18.31 mA/cm^2 at a defect density of 10^{10}cm^{-2} to 13.20 mA/cm^2 at the efficiency defect density of 10^{14}cm^{-2} , F.F increases from 37.69% at the defect density of 10^{10}cm^{-2} to 46.87% at the defect density of 10^{14}cm^{-2} , η decreases from 4.51% at the defect density of 10^{10}cm^{-2} to 4.01% at the defect density of 10^{14}cm^{-2} . The reason for this decrease is due to an increase in the union rate, which leads to a decrease in quantitative efficiency, as in Figure (3).

In the case of the donor alum, the results show that V_{oc} , J_{sc} , F.F, and η are not affected by the change in the defect level in the case of the donor alum, because all the interfacial states within this energy range lie below the Fermi level, and this leads to filling these states and transforming them into a neutral state. The reason for all of the above is that the bundle diagram in the case of donor alum is identical to the bundle diagram in the case of neutral (neutral).

Figure 3 Quantum efficiency with varying interfacial defects

4.2. Effect of interfacial defect concentration and carrier trapping cross section

The carrier capture cross section (C_n , C_p) has a significant impact on the electrical properties of the solar cell because the carrier capture cross section has a relationship with the carrier durability and the propagation length, and this is consistent with equation (2-49). As the cross-section of carrier capture increases, the length of propagation will decrease, and thus the durability of the carriers will decrease.

In this part, the density of the interfacial defects was changed from (10^{10}) to (10^{14}) cm^{-2} and the trapping cross-section from (10^{-12} - (10^{-16}) cm^2 . The results showed as shown in Figure (4), a decrease in V_{oc} with an increase The cross-section ranges from 0.791 V to 0.776 V, J_{sc} from 27.69 (mA/cm^2) to 20.60 (mA/cm^2), F.F from 84.59% to 70.21%, and η from 18.53% to 11.24%, and the reason for this is due to the increase in surface union. For electron-gap pairs, which leads to a decrease in the concentration of carriers as shown in Figure (5a), and we also notice a decrease in quantum efficiency (QE) with an increase in the density of interfacial defects as in Figure (5b).

Figure 4 The effect of the trapping cross section and the density of interfacial defects on the operation of the solar cell

Figure 5 [a] hole current density when changing $Cn=Cp$ [b] Quantum efficiency at each interfacial defect density

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we have studied the Effects of interfacial defects of the p-CuO/n-TiO₂ on solar cells using SCAPS-1D. However, these results show a decrease in Voc, Jsc, and η with increasing interfacial defect density. The reason for this decrease is due to an increase in the recombination rate, which leads to a decrease in quantitative efficiency, as in Figure (3).

On the other hand, The carrier capture cross section (C_n, C_p) has a significant impact on the electrical properties of the solar cell because the carrier capture cross section has a relationship with the carrier durability and the propagation length. As the cross-section The results showed as shown in Figure (4), a decrease in Voc, Jsc, F.F and η , with an increase in the cross-section. The cross-section ranges and the reason for this is due to the increase in surface recombination. For electron-hole pairs, which leads to a decrease in the concentration of carriers as shown in Figure (5a), and we also notice a decrease in quantum efficiency (QE) with an increase in the density of interfacial defects as in Figure (5b).

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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